

1 TITLE

2 Quantitative Raman Spectroscopy as a tool to study the kinetics and formation
3 mechanism of Carbonates

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25 ABSTRACT

26 We describe a systematic study of the abiotic precipitation at different temperatures of
27 several Mg and Ca carbonates (calcite, nesquehonite, hydrocalcite) present in
28 carbonaceous chondrites. This study highlights the capability of Raman spectroscopy as
29 a primary tool to perform a full mineralogical analysis. The precipitation reaction and
30 the structure of the resulted carbonates were monitored and identified with Raman
31 spectroscopy. Raman spectroscopy allows us to confirm that the precipitation reaction is
32 very fast (minutes) when Ca(II) is present in the solution, whereas for Mg(II) such
33 reactions develop at rather quite slow rates (weeks). We also observe that both the
34 composition and the reaction mechanisms depend on the temperature, which might help
35 to clarify several issues concerning the planetological/geological field, because the
36 environmental implications of these carbonates on both terrestrial and extraterrestrial
37 objects.

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39 KEYWORDS

40 Raman spectroscopy; X-Ray Diffraction; Carbonates; Precipitation; Kinetics.

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42 1. INTRODUCTION

43 Carbonaceous chondrites contain primitive materials originated during the formation of
44 the Solar System. These meteorites have suffered different degrees of alteration in their
45 respective parent body and the analysis of the alteration minerals has allowed
46 establishing a rational classification. Secondary minerals, such as carbonates and
47 sulfates, result from hydrothermal alteration, thus being indicative of the presence of
48 water. Among the carbonaceous chondrites, both types CI and CM contain several
49 carbonates, mainly calcite / aragonite (CaCO_3), breunnerite ($\text{Mg}(\text{Fe},\text{Mn})(\text{CO}_3)$),
50 dolomite ($\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$), magnesite (MgCO_3) and siderite (FeCO_3) [1]. Isotopic and
51 mineralogical studies on some of these carbonates show that the temperature of the
52 forming fluids in these minerals depends on the chondrite class where they are present
53 [1]. For instance, in CM carbonaceous chondrites, the forming temperature could reach
54 values even lower than 293 K (20°C) [2].

55 Terrestrial weathering of meteorites also modifies the primitive materials through
56 several chemical processes: oxidation of metals, hydrolysis of silicates, hydration,
57 carbonation, and solution. There are a percentage of carbonaceous chondrites found in
58 Antarctica that include white efflorescence minerals, which are mainly magnesium
59 carbonates with different degrees of hydration, in particular, nesquehonite
60 ($\text{MgCO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and hydromagnesite ($\text{Mg}_5(\text{CO}_3)_4(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$). The analysis of these
61 carbonates revealed that they formed by weathering of the meteorites at terrestrial
62 conditions near freezing temperatures. Such temperatures are similar than those in the
63 alteration environment of asteroids in the early solar system [3]. The cations are
64 obtained by hydrolysis of ferromagnesian silicates and glass, while the anion is
65 produced by a carbonating solution of a fluid enriched in atmospheric CO_2 [4, 5]. The

66 nesquehonite transforms to hydromagnesite at temperatures above 52°C by losing CO₂
67 and water [6, 7]. Hänchen et al. [8] have reported a detailed study about the effect of the
68 temperature and CO₂ pressure on the precipitation of Mg-carbonates. These authors
69 show at 25°C and 1 bar pressure of CO₂ (g) nesquehonite precipitates from carbonate
70 solutions, and nesquehonite transformations to hydromagnesite at temperatures above
71 about 50°C.

72 The objective of this work is to demonstrate the suitability of Raman spectroscopy to
73 study the abiotic formation at atmospheric pressure of Ca(II) and Mg(II) carbonates
74 from bicarbonate solutions within the temperature range (i.e. 4, 20 and 50 °C) of the
75 aqueous alteration occurring in carbonaceous chondrites Raman and FT-IR spectra of
76 calcium and magnesium carbonates have been previously studied by several authors [7],
77 and also have been used with other techniques to study the kinetic reaction of the Mg-
78 carbonate from carbonate solutions [8]. In particular, Raman spectroscopy allowed us
79 to study: (1) the kinetics of formation at different temperatures of Mg-carbonates and
80 (2) the structure of the precipitated Mg- and Ca-carbonates, which are compared with
81 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) results.

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83 2. EXPERIMENTAL

84 Sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃), calcium perchlorate (Ca(ClO₄)₂), magnesium
85 perchlorate (Mg(ClO₄)₂) and sodium perchlorate (NaClO₄) were purchased from Sigma-
86 Aldrich and used without further purification (pro analysis, > 99%). MilliQ water, with
87 total organic carbon lower than 10 ppb and resistivity higher than 18 mΩ cm⁻¹, was used
88 as solvent.

89 Raman spectra were excited with a 532 nm line of a solid state laser. After passing a
90 monochromator (Horiba JobinYvon HRi 550, equipped with diffraction gratings of
91 1200, 1800 and 2400 grooves/mm), the scattered light was detected with a Charged
92 Couple Device (CCD). Fiber optics is used to connect both spectrometer and laser (100
93 μm and 50 μm , respectively) to the optical probe head. It was employed a diffraction
94 grating with 1200 grooves/mm. The spectral resolution of the present experiments
95 exceeds 2 cm^{-1} .

96 Micrographs were made with gold-coated samples using a JEOL -5600 LV scanning
97 electron microscope, (SEM).

98 Angle-dispersive X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements on the samples were carried
99 out with an Xcalibur diffractometer. XRD patterns using $K_{\alpha 1}$: $K_{\alpha 2}$ molybdenum
100 radiation were recorded on a 135 mm Atlas CCD detector placed at 110 mm from the
101 sample.

102 Solutions were first prepared at the corresponding molar concentrations listed in Table 1
103 with a magnetic stirring in a round-flask equipped with a septum. For the preparation of
104 bicarbonate solutions, and in order to minimize the loss of bicarbonate as CO_2 (g), the
105 round-flask equipped is equipped with a septum, and after the completely dissolution of
106 the solid by very slow stirring (around 8 hours), the pH of the initial solutions is
107 measurement, (see Table 2). The solutions were kept at the reaction temperature
108 overnight before starting the experiments. Then, 10mL of the bicarbonate solution
109 (NaHCO_3) was poured drop wise with a syringe into the round-flask containing the 10
110 mL of the perchlorate solution. All precipitation reactions were performed in round-
111 flask equipment with a septum without any stirring. The initial time of the reaction is
112 considered when the last drop of NaHCO_3 is added, and the initial concentration is the

113 real concentration prepared for each reaction. Thereby, an aliquot of the supernatant of
114 approximately 0.3 mL is taken for each measuring time without further filtration and its
115 Raman spectrum is recorded at room temperature. The sampling time depends on the
116 reaction, e.i. when the Ca^{2+} is present in the reaction, the precipitation rate is very fast
117 and we had measured the bicarbonate concentration at initial conditions and after the
118 reaction is finished and, when Mg^{2+} is present in the reaction, the precipitation rate is
119 slow, therefore we had sampling the reaction, taking an aliquots, each some days or
120 weeks depending on the variation of the bicarbonate concentration.

121 3. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

122 Carbonate syntheses were performed from sodium bicarbonate NaHCO_3 and, as a
123 source of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} , $\text{Ca}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, respectively, in a stequiometric 2:1
124 of $\text{Mg}:\text{HCO}_3$ and $\text{Ca}:\text{HCO}_3$ respectively.

125 The kinetics of the reaction was studied by measuring the decrease in concentration of
126 the bicarbonate ion at the supernatant, using quantitative Raman spectroscopy (QRS).
127 The Raman spectra of NaClO_4 and NaHCO_3 in the 800 to 4000 wavenumbers spectral
128 range are shown in Figure 1. The most intense band of the perchlorate ion is found *ca.*
129 930 cm^{-1} and corresponds to the Cl-O stretch. For the bicarbonate ion the most
130 prominent feature (C-OH stretch) appears around 1017 cm^{-1} . Since these peaks do not
131 overlap, the Raman analysis of the peak height, proportional to integrated intensity,
132 gives us a measure of the $\text{HCO}_3^-/\text{ClO}_4^-$ relative concentration and allows constructing a
133 calibration curve in order to analyse the precipitation reaction. Figure 2 shows selected
134 spectra of different aqueous solutions of sodium perchlorate (NaClO_4) at 0.3 M, and
135 sodium hydrogen-carbonate (NaHCO_3) over a wide range of concentrations (see
136 calibration solutions in Table 1) at room temperature. All spectra were normalized

137 relative to the height of the 930 cm^{-1} wavenumber band of the perchlorate ion, which is
138 used as internal pattern, since its concentration is constant in each calibration solution.
139 Figure 2 shows the decrease in height of the 1017 cm^{-1} band as the concentration of
140 HCO_3^- decreases. It should be note that in the concentration range studied we did not
141 found widening of this band, and that the calibration have been done at room
142 temperature to avoid the different changes in the Raman signal due to the change in
143 temperature and the supernatant of the reaction is also analysed at the same room
144 temperature. The relative height of the 1017 cm^{-1} band have been calculates by fitting
145 the peak to a lorentzian shape functions. These calculated heights depend linearly on the
146 molar concentration of bicarbonate ion (inset in Fig. 2) with a correlation factor of 0.99
147 and a proportionality constant of (0.339 ± 0.007) . This calibration equation allows us to
148 calculate the concentration of HCO_3^- at any time in the precipitation, and therefore, the
149 amount of $\text{MCO}_3(\text{s})$ formed as a function of time at any temperature.

150 We have analyzed the kinetics of the reaction with $\text{M} = \text{Ca}$ at three different
151 temperatures 4, 20 and 50°C , ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) observing that the reaction is extremely fast at
152 any temperature, and the initial concentration of HCO_3^- is consumed in less than one
153 hour, (see Fig.3 as an example), Therefore, it has been impossible to follow the kinetic
154 reaction of the Ca- carbonates at any temperature. It should be noted that, even at very
155 dilute concentrations, the kinetics of the reaction in too fast to be measured in our setup
156 (experiments not shown), and that the analysis of the supernatant shows that the
157 concentration of bicarbonate do not change during two weeks, therefore we assume that
158 the precipitation reaction from HCO_3^- is finished.

159 After the reaction is finished, we filter the solution, selecting several crystal specimens
160 for structural analysis. Two possible carbonate solid structures of carbonates are

161 possible when Ca(II) is present in the medium: Calcite (trigonal) and Aragonite
162 (orthorhombic). As is shown in Figure 5, Raman spectroscopy can distinguish between
163 mineral polymorphs through analysis of the lattice modes appearing below 300
164 wavenumbers. The main band of calcium carbonates at $\sim 1085\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to the
165 symmetric stretching ν_1 vibration, and is similar for both structures. The lattice modes
166 however vary with the crystalline structure. Slightly different Raman shifts can also be
167 found for the in-plane bending ν_2 vibration (*ca.* 700 wavenumbers) and for the anti-
168 symmetric stretch vibration (ν_3 , *ca.* 1450 wavenumbers), as revealed in the high
169 resolution spectra. Using the assignment described above, the calcium carbonates
170 precipitated at different temperatures were identified as calcites, as shown in the lower
171 spectrum of Figure 4.

172 We found an opposite behaviour in the precipitation reaction when Mg^{2+} was present in
173 solution. The initial concentration of bicarbonate decreases very slowly and the
174 decrease has different behaviour depending on the temperature, as can be seen in Fig. 5
175 where the concentration of HCO_3^- is represented as a function of time at different
176 temperatures.

177 In order to analyse the kinetic of the reaction we have calculated the precipitation rate,
178 v , as

$$-dC/dt = v, \quad (2)$$

179 where C is the concentration of HCO_3^- . By plotting the logarithmic of the precipitation
180 rate vs. the logarithmic of the concentration of bicarbonate, (inset in Figure 6), we have
181 calculated the order of the reaction, α , and the rate coefficient, K , as described by
182 Equation 3:

$$v = K C^{\alpha}; \log v = \log K + \alpha \log C \quad (3)$$

183 As can be seen in the inset in Figure 5, there is a constant decay of the v for the
184 precipitation performed at 4°C and 20°C whereas that at 50°C this behaviour only occur
185 up to a concentration of $\text{HCO}_3^- \sim 0.15$ M, from which the precipitation rate drops very
186 fast to zero, i.e. the precipitation reaction bicarbonate finish because all HCO_3^- is
187 consumed.

188 In Table 3, the calculated parameter, K and α are shown. The precipitation rate increases
189 strongly with increasing temperature as the expected Arrhenius behaviour, and affects
190 deeply to the mechanism of the reaction, (see the different order of reaction obtained for
191 each temperature). The precipitations performed at 4°C and 20°C are close to a first
192 order reaction, ($\alpha = 1$ and 1.2 respectively) and in these precipitated reactions the
193 amount excess of HCO_3^- is close to zero; whereas at 50°C the order of the reaction is
194 higher ($\alpha = 3.6$) and the reaction ends when the concentration of bicarbonate is almost
195 half of the initial concentration. Taking into account that all reaction were performed at
196 stoichiometric conditions (1:1 of $\text{Mg}:\text{HCO}_3^-$), we can assume that the carbonate product
197 has the same stoichiometry 1:1 for the reaction at 4 °C and 20 °C which could
198 correspond to nesquehonite structure, $\text{MgCO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and the product stoichiometry
199 could be 2:1, ($\text{Mg} : \text{HCO}_3^-$) for 50°C which agrees with the chemical formula of the
200 hydromagnesite, $\text{MgCO}_3\text{Mg}(\text{OH})4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Therefore, the changes in the velocity of the
201 reactions at 4 and 20°C can be explained by the effect of the temperature reaction,
202 whereas the different kinetics observed in the reaction performed at 50°C is due to two
203 reasons the formation of different phases at different temperatures and the higher
204 temperature.

205 The formation of hydromagnesite from nesquehonite at high temperature ($< 50^{\circ}\text{C}$) have
206 been previously studied [6, 7, 8, 9 and 10]. For example Davis and Bubela [6] showed
207 that nesquehonite can be altered to hydromagnesite via an intermediated phase with
208 similar X-ray pattern to dypingite ($4\text{MgCO}_3 \cdot \text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) but by using “in situ”
209 Raman spectroscopy Hänchen et al. 2008 [8] have reported that at temperatures above
210 50°C nesquehonite transforms to hydromagnesite without any intermediate phase.

211 The result of this work shows that the hydromagnesite can be precipitated from
212 bicarbonate at 50°C and that this reaction has different kinetic that the reactions at lower
213 temperatures in which the resulting phase were nesquehonite, which may be explained
214 by different mechanism of reactions at different temperatures.

215

216 **Raman** Figure 6

217 We analyzed the solid structure by X-Ray Diffraction and Scanning Electron
218 Microscopy in order to check the obtained results of the magnesium and calcium
219 carbonates by Raman spectroscopy. Figure 7 shows the X-Ray diffractograms and the
220 SEM images for the precipitated carbonates. The diffractograms corresponding to the
221 calcium carbonates precipitated at different temperatures were all indexed into a calcite
222 structure. For magnesium carbonates we identified two different structures;
223 nesquehonite, $\text{MgCO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, at low temperature ($4 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $20 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and
224 hydromagnesite, $\text{Mg}_5(\text{CO}_3)_4(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 4(\text{H}_2\text{O})$, at high temperature ($50 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$). Note that
225 all these results are in perfect agreement with the Raman results (Figure 8) and previous
226 studies [11, 12 and 13]. SEM images also shows the different mineral habits of each
227 mineral, which are in agreement with those found by other authors [6, 7, 8, 9, 11].

228 4. CONCLUSIONS

229 We have shown that Raman spectroscopy is a powerful tool to analysis the abiotic
230 precipitation of Mg and Ca carbonates at different temperatures. This technique allowed
231 us to analyze the kinetic of the reaction of Mg-carbonates and, after the precipitation,
232 the crystalline structure of Ca and Mg-carbonates. Moreover, by using this technique we
233 were able to relate the kinetic of the reaction with the structures of the Mg- carbonates
234 studied, which is the fundamental importance to highlight questions in the field of
235 carbonates. There are still some conflicts in the literature with the natural occurrence of
236 nesquehonite and other carbonate minerals [4, 6, 14, 15, 16]. The results of this paper
237 confirm that even if the weathering of the Antarctic meteorites is very short, it is
238 possible the formation of calcite and nesquehonite, once the bicarbonate is formed.
239 Although the formation of the lansfordite phase, $MgCO_3 \cdot 5 H_2O$, as the precursor
240 mineral which precipitates at lower temperatures has been invoked [14, 15] our results
241 show that nesquehonite crystallizes directly at 4 and 20 °C and at 50°C hydromagnesite
242 precipitate following a different mechanism that at lower temperatures.

243 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

244 This work was supported by Comunidad de Madrid and the EU through QUIMAPRES
245 project (S2009/PPQ-1551) and by MICINN through MALTA Consolider (CSD2007-
246 00045), CTQ2009-14596-C02-01 and CTQ2012-38599-C02-02 projects.

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248 REFERENCES

- 249 [1] S. Leuv, A.E. Rubin, J.T. Wasson, *Meteorit. Planet. Sci.* 45 (2010) 73-90.
- 250 [2] R.N. Clayton, T.K. Mayeda, *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 67 (1984) 151-161.
- 251 [3] P.A. Bland, M.E. Zolensky, G.K. Benedix, M.A. Septhon, *Meteorites and the Early*
252 *Solar System II*, University of Arizona Press, Tucson, 2006.
- 253 [4] M.A. Velbel, D.T. Long, J.L. Gooding, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 55 (1991) 67-
254 76.
- 255 [5] M.M. Grady, I.P. Wright, E.K. Gibson Jr., C.T. Pillinger, *Meteoritics* 24 (1989) 1-7.
- 256 [6] P.J. Davies, B. Bubela, *Chem. Geol.* 12 (1973) 289-300.
- 257 [7] L. Hopkinson, K. Rutt, G. Cressey, *J. Geol. (Chicago, IL, U.S.)* 116 (2008) 387-400.
- 258 [8] M. Hänchen, V. Prigiobbe, R. Baciocchi, M. Mazzotti, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 63 (2008)
259 1012-1028.
- 260 [9] Z. Zhang, Y. Zheng, Y. Ni, Z. Liu, J. Chen, X. Liang, *J. Phys. Chem. B* 110 (2006)
261 12969-12973.
- 262 [10] J. Lanas, J.I. Alvarez, *Thermochimica Acta* 421 (2004) 123-132.
- 263 [11] J.T. Kloprogge, W.N. Martens, L. Nothdurft, V. Duong, G.E. Webb, *J. Mater. Sci.*
264 *Lett.* 22 (2003) 825-829.
- 265 [12] H.G.M Edwards, S.E. Jorge Villar, J. Jehlicka, T. Munshi, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part*
266 *A* 61 (2005) 2273-2280.
- 267 [13] R.L. Frost, M.C. Hales, W.N. Martens, *J. Raman Spectrosc.* 39 (2008) 1141-1149.
- 268 [14] R.A. Robie, B.S. Hemingway, *Am. Mineral.*, 57 (1972) 1768-1781.
- 269 [15] R.A. Robie & B.S. Hemingway, *U. S. Geol. Surv. J. Res.* 5 (1973) 543-547.
- 270 [16] E. Königsberger, L.C. Königsberger, H. Gamsjäger, *Geochimica et Cosmochimica*
271 *Acta*, 63 (1999) 3105-3119.
- 272 [17] D. Langmuir, *J. Geol. (Chicago, IL, U.S.)* 73 (1965) 730-754.

273 [18] D. W. Ming. Thesis. Chemical and crystalline properties of minerals in the MgO-
274 CO₂-H₂O system. (1981), Colorado State University.
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279 Figure 1

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300 Figura 6

301 La estamos haciendo

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316 Figure Captions

317 Fig. 1 Raman spectra from 800 to 4000 cm^{-1} of two aqueous solution of (a) NaClO_4
318 0.3M and (b) NaHCO_3 0.6M

319 Fig. 2 Raman spectra of different aqueous solutions of NaClO_4 (0.3M) and NaHCO_3
320 (0.1 - 0.6M), respectively. The inset shows the calibration curve obtained from the
321 spectra shown at different molar concentrations of the bicarbonate ion.

322 Fig. 3 Raman spectra obtained at the initial time (grey line) and after one hour reaction
323 (black line) respectively, of the Reaction 1 with $M = \text{Ca}$ at $(4 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$.

324 Fig. 4 Typical Raman spectra of calcite and aragonite. The lower Raman spectrum
325 corresponds to the precipitate obtained in Reaction 1.

326 Fig. 5 Molar concentration of HCO_3^- vs. minutes of reaction, corresponding to the
327 precipitation reactions of magnesium carbonate at 4, 20 and 50°C . Inset in the
328 logarithmic of the precipitation rate (v) vs. the logarithmic of the concentration of
329 bicarbonate, C .

330 Fig. 6 Typical Raman spectra of nesquehonite and hydromagnesite obtained in Reaction
331 4, 5 and 6.

332 Fig. 7 X-Ray diffractograms and the SEM images for the magnesium (left) and calcium
333 carbonates (right).

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337 TABLE 1. Molar concentrations of the calibration solutions

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Calibration solutions	NaHCO ₃ (mol/L)	NaClO ₄ (mol/L)
1	0.6	0.6
2	0.5	0.6
3	0.4	0.6
4	0.3	0.6
5	0.2	0.6
6	0.1	0.6

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341 TABLE 2 Reactions and molar concentration of each reactive

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Reaction	T (°C)	NaHCO ₃ (mol/L) / pHi	Ca(ClO ₄) ₂ (mol/L)	Mg(ClO ₄) ₂ (mol/L)
1	4	0.3 / 7.97	0.15	0
2	20	0.3 / 7.89	0.15	0
3	50	0.3 / 8.10	0.15	0
4	4	0.3 / 7.99	0	0.15
5	20	0.3 / 7.90	0	0.15
6	50	0.3 / 8.07	0	0.15

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349 TABLE 3 Rate coefficient, K , and order of the reaction, α .

Reaction	T (°C)	K	α
4	4	$(6.4 \pm 0.2)10^{-5}$	1.2 ± 0.1
5	20	$(1.6 \pm 0.2)10^{-4}$	1.0 ± 0.1
6	50	$(2.4 \pm 0.2)10^{-3}$	3.6 ± 0.1

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